

Scientific Storytelling

Using the S-P-R-E Pattern to Conceptualise Research Activities

The **Situation, Problem, Response, Evaluation** pattern (S-P-R-E, or Problem-Solution pattern) is found in many texts, spanning genres and cultures (Hoey, Winter). For researchers, it can be used to structure not only thoughts, but also research, writing, and other scientific communication activities (Edge & Wharton). Because almost all academic/scientific discourse is based on variations of this pattern, researchers can benefit from an understanding of it when they are planning projects, designing presentations, or writing proposals, abstracts, reports, articles, theses, or dissertations (Haas).

It is not necessary for the individual S-P-R-E elements to be presented separately (they are often fused); they need not always appear in the order shown here; and elements will recur throughout the text. Furthermore, different disciplines employ the pattern in different ways, using different terminology to describe the pattern elements, having different preferred orders, and different proportions of attention paid to each element. Regardless of discipline, language, order, or emphasis, the following components will almost invariably appear in research stories that feel 'complete' to a reader (or listener).

Situation

- **State**
This is what we already know; what other researchers have already done. This is the more general 'state of the art'— the broader picture of other research that has been done on issues relevant to the current research project. This is sometimes called 'research background, ' or 'grounding'.
- **Setting**
This is the research context—the particular environment in which a research project is being conducted; it is the local conditions in which a researcher is working in order to contribute to a broader research conversation.
- **So What?**
It should *always* be clear, both to researchers themselves and to readers/listeners, *why* a study is being done. In some cases, the motivation is implicit in, or fused with, the Problem. Regardless of how it is reported to a wider audience, researchers can often re-visit their own motivations for starting

research projects, and why they are important, relevant, or useful. This helps keep you on track when things get messy and muddled.

Problem

This is the precise question that the researcher aims to answer—right here, right now, in this research project.

The Problem might be—but is not necessarily—a practical, real-world problem. It could also signify a gap in our understanding that a researcher hopes to fill. The problem could simply be “we don’t know this yet.” Depending on the discipline, the Problem might be referred to as focus, hypothesis, research question, research aim, objectives, etc.

Response

This is the action taken; it’s what researchers actually *do* in response to the problem. It is sometimes called ‘methodology’, ‘materials and methods’ or ‘procedures’ etc., this element includes information on how the research was conducted, and the underlying reasoning/theories/models that justify research decisions. The response can be sub-divided into two conceptual components (Edge):

- Principles
These are the research paradigms/theories/frameworks/reasons/models/tools and justifications underlying research decisions and actions
- Procedures
These are the precise steps a researcher takes to answer their research question(s) or address the research problem(s)
 - Data collection methods and procedures
 - Data analysis methods and procedures

Note: ‘method’ indicates data collection/analysis tools used; ‘procedures’ indicates specifically how tools were used to collect/analyse the data; ‘methodology’ normally includes the underlying theories or logic driving the actions of a researcher

Evaluation

The Evaluation can include the results of the data analysis, an interpretation of the results, an evaluation of the research project itself, any limitations, any practical applications, and will often point to future research.

- Results
The objective reporting of findings of your (data) analysis
- Discussion/Implications/Conclusions
It is often not enough for researchers to simply report results. To fully represent the story the data have to tell, the researcher might also need to interpret, discuss, and draw conclusions. If this part is neglected, a reader or listener might well ask, “So what?” An audience should not be left asking questions like, “What does this mean?” or “How is this important?” or “How can we use this?”

Any claims made in interpretations of data or conclusions drawn must be based on analysis, and need to be argued using support from the data and/or literature.

- Limitations
Every research project has its limitations; research always “could have been better if...” Ethically, these limitations should be transparently reported. Note that ‘limitations’ assumed that the researchers did the absolute best they possibly could given the research circumstances. It means that thorough, principled research was conducted within the parameters in which a researcher was working. It does *not mean* that researchers can validate half-assed work.
- Further Research
All research is complete and incomplete: each project aims to answer one small question, but it is always part of much bigger questions. Research that is done well should also point to how things can be taken further in order to move our understanding of questions (big and small) forward.

Partial Reference List:

This handout is informed by my ongoing interviews with writers, and the analysis of academic texts, from 18 (so far) different disciplines. It also relies heavily on the insights, research, and work of others—particularly that of Winter, and Hoey, who first brought the SPRE pattern to the world’s attention, and Edge, who brought it to my attention in 2002. A more extensive reference list can be found in Haas, 2012.

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